

IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF LONG FIBER THERMOPLASTIC (LFT) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Long Fiber Thermoplastics (LFT) with polypropylene (PP) matrix with varying percentage of glass fiber is increasingly being used in the automotive sector as underbody shields and side panels. LFT in this work are classified as materials with fiber lengths of 25-50 mm. The LFT parts used in transportation applications are susceptible to blunt object impact (BOI) such as flying debris, stones/rocks and tool drops. These effects are of great concern, although not well studied. There are currently no standard test methods that address impact threats from such common phenomena such as BOI. Traditional impact data for thermoplastics is generated by the notched-Izod impact test, which does not correlate to common impacts such as BOI. In the present study, impact damage resistance of extrusion-compression molded LFT - PP is assessed for its damage and energy absorption characteristics by a gas-gun impactor. The compression-molded panels are manufactured from LFT pellets. The compression molding process creates preferential fiber orientation of the long fibers. This paper presents results on BOI damage to LFT glass/PP panels. The damage response, energy absorption characteristics and damage modes of the LFT panels are investigated.

KEY WORDS: Long Fiber Thermoplastics, Blunt Object Impact

INTRODUCTION

The use of thermoplastic composites has gained steady favor over traditional materials such as steel in structural and semi-structural applications. The current US market for such materials is in excess of one billion pounds per annum, half of which is consumed by the automotive industry [1,2]. This usage is due to properties such as specific strength, damping, corrosion resistance, and impact properties. Moreover, closed molded LFTs share the attractive features of high volume processability, ability to fill complex geometries, intrinsic recyclability, and the capacity of part integration.

Thermoplastic composites are typically comprised of a cost-effective commodity matrix such as polypropylene, polyethylene, nylon, etc; reinforced with glass, carbon and/or aramid fibers. E-glass is the most common reinforcement since the market niche is driven more by cost/performance ratio than weight/performance ratio, as demanded by the aerospace industry. Injection molded short fiber thermoplastic composites (fiber lengths less than 2 mm) are currently the most pervasive of the aforementioned composites, although the full advantage of the reinforcing fiber is not realized due to the low fiber aspect ratio. Glass Mat Thermoplastics (GMTs) consist of a chopped or continuous fiber mat reinforcement in a thermoplastic matrix. Preparation is done by melt impregnation of non-woven glass mat (dry route) or by mixing chopped fiber with polymer powder in a fluid medium (wet route), both of which are heated in a GMT oven prior to compression molding [3]. Injection, injection-compression, and

extrusion-compression molding techniques are employed for LFT processing. LFT fiber lengths are typically greater than 12 mm depending on the desired properties, fiber concentration, and processing technique. In the present work the average fiber lengths are 25 mm. The fiber aspect ratio of about 2000 in case of LFT allows realizing the fiber strength in contrast to its short fiber complement [4].

As the use of LFTs continues to grow in automotive and other industries, the need to determine their impact properties increases, to ensure the safety and stability of the designed structures [5]. Few authors have attempted to characterize the impact performance of discontinuous, randomly oriented LFT panels. Those that have focused primarily on Charpy and Izod impact testing, and to an even lesser degree, low velocity drop tower impact testing [6]. Very little work, if any, has looked into the effect of intermediate velocity (10 m/s-100 m/s) BOI on LFTs. These velocity ranges simulate the effects of tool drops, service/maintenance induced damage, blunt objects (such as rocks and debris) while traveling at highway speeds, as well as impacts induced by debris from hurricanes and tornadoes for storm shelter and military housing applications.

A considerable amount of work has gone into studying impact on continuous fiber thermoset matrix composite structures [7-10]. An understanding of LFT behavior while undergoing high energy; high strain rate impact is essential in promoting implementation of its use in automotive and other markets. Charpy and Izod type impact test configurations are limited in terms of specimen size, impact direction, and boundary conditions [5]. A more representative test would be the BOI test because it simulates events such as debris/stone hits on underside or side panels of vehicles.

MATERIALS

The material considered was BP Amoco 109961 (PP) resin, glass fiber John Mansfield 840-BC-225, average fiber length 12.5 mm chips, 40% fiber weight fraction, 2.5% 3200 polybond additive and 1% Schulman 3200 heat stabilizer. LFT pellets were formed using a hot melt process, and then fed into a plasticator and a charge (shot) extruded. The charge was placed on a tool and compression molded to produce plaques. LFT plaques of size 210 mm x 210 mm for BOI with nominal plate thickness 5 mm were used. The average weight and standard deviation (S.D.) for the BOI samples was 206.32 g (S.D.= 1.358 g), 219.8 g (S.D.= 1.822 g), 225.27 g (S.D.= 1.056 g). The average areal density corresponded to 0.439 g/cm², 0.467 g/cm², and 0.479 g/cm².

EXPERIMENTAL

Intermediate velocities between 10 and 100 m/s simulate the effect of blunt objects such as rocks and debris for automobiles traveling at highway speeds. A gas-gun which propels a variety of projectiles over a velocity range of approximately 10 m/s to 100 m/s was used. The gun consists of a 3 m long barrel, firing valve, and capture chamber, which holds the specimen. Two phases of testing were conducted using sabots of 38.1 mm diameter - a) using flat end cylindrical aluminum sabot of 100 gms, and b) two ultra high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) sabots each of mass of 25 gms, one with a flat end, and the other with a shallow conical tipped end. The rationale for the tests was based upon in-situ video observations of the impact event, where slight tumbling of a flat projectile resulted in penetration upon contact with a sharp edge, thereby resembling a pointed end contact.

Two chronographs (Model – ProChrono Digital) were mounted with clamps to the bottom of the capture chamber with a transparent optical window to record the incident and residual velocity of the projectile. Varying the pressure of gas in the firing chamber varied the impact velocity. A calibration curve was generated to establish the relationship of the pressure to projectile velocity. The highest energy is absorbed at the ballistic limit of the material, at which the projectile actually embeds in the specimen.

Five samples were tested for each test configuration in an attempt to accurately determine the critical (or ballistic limit) velocity. This is similar to the V_{50} ballistic limit, which is defined in terms of the projectile having a 50% probability of completely penetrating the specimen at the critical velocity. A simply supported boundary condition on two sides with the supports 160 mm apart was considered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase 1 tests: 100 gms projectile with a cylindrical aluminum sabot with flat end: The initial results for energy vs. areal density are shown in Fig. 1. For samples with areal density of 0.430 g/cm^2 and 0.467 g/cm^2 , the impact response in terms of energy absorption was of similar magnitude (approximately 155 J), while for the 0.479 g/cm^2 specimens, the energy absorbed was higher by about 7%. As the areal density increases, the energy absorbed increases. Representative damage is shown in Fig. 2. The impact of a 100-gms projectile was recorded using a high-speed camera with 14,000 pictures/s, providing $40 \mu\text{s}$ exposures. About 25 mm maximum deformation was observed in flexure combined with torsional oscillations of the panel during the course of the impact, from the high-speed photography tests. For panels with normal incidence (i.e., full contact of the face of the projectile to the sample) of impact, the limiting damage occurred by punch through and simultaneous tearing across planes of lower fiber volume and/or concentration. In most of the tests, the edge of the projectile made contact due to slight tilting of the projectile upon or prior to contact, and caused the initial notch, followed by punch-through and tearing. The velocity for penetration of the plaques was 54 m/s, and the maximum energy absorbed was approximately 145 J for the sample with areal density 0.439 g/cm^2 .

Figure 1. Blunt object impact tests. Energy vs Areal Density. Squared data points represent full penetration

Figure 2. Sample 020919-1-33b
K.E. = 148.4 J, 100 g sabot

Phase 2 tests: 50 gms projectiles with flat and pointed ends: The influence of different projectile geometries impacting the LFT plaque was studied in order to understand how contact influences penetration. Results for the 50 gms flat and conically tipped UHMWPE projectiles are shown in Fig. 3. The flat tipped projectile had an overall length of 48 mm with an actual mass of 50.56 g, while the conically tipped projectile had an overall length of 54 mm with a 60° shoulder and an actual mass of 49.83 g. The statistical significance of the results is given in Table 1. Trends for both impactors show a linear relationship between impact energy dissipation and areal density, where three different areal densities were investigated. On an average, the conically tipped projectile exhibited about 26% less energy than the flat tipped projectile for penetration. The decrease in energy is thought to come from the high contact stresses developed at the tip of the conical projectile, i.e. the area at which the damage initiates, as shown in Fig. 4. In both cases however, the fracture path tends to follow planes of high fiber orientation in which the resistance to shearing is the least. This was verified through observation of the fracture surface on a SEM. A representative optical micrograph, taken at 200 X, is shown in Fig. 4.

Table 1. Statistical significance of the impact test results on LFT for a 50 g Projectile

Projectile	S.D. (J)	95% C.I (J)	Mean (J)	Areal Density (g cm ⁻²)
50 g Flat	20.5	13.4	146.4	0.439
50 g Conical	13.4	11.7	110.5	
50 g Flat	26.4	19.6	174.9	0.467
50 g Conical	16.4	14.4	126.1	
50 g Flat	21.1	18.5	178.4	0.479
50 g Conical	12.9	11.3	134.3	

Fig. 3. Energy Dissipation vs. Areal Density for 50 g flat and conically tipped projectiles for LFT (PP/E-Glass) specimens with varying areal density.

Fig. 4. Representative LFT panels impacted by flat (a) and conical (b) projectiles. In both cases, the projectile perforated the specimen. Note the shear zone (shear plugging) created by the flat projectile along the periphery of the impact area as opposed the small shear zone created by the conically tipped projectile in which the damage progresses radially from the high contact stress area.

SUMMARY

The LFT plaques supported at two sides fixed and two sides free, exhibited almost 25 mm dynamic deflection and repeated torsional-flexural vibrations of the panel during BOI by a flat end aluminum sabot (blunt object), without visible damage up to areal density dependent threshold energy. For example, the threshold energy for the samples with areal density of 0.439 g/cm² was 148 J. The failure occurred by shear punch-through and simultaneous cracking along preferential path of the long fibers. Matrix cracking occurred at preferential orientation of the fibers, i.e., the orientation which develops during the compression molding process. Fiber pull-out and breakage were dominant failure modes.

Fig. 3. Representative SEM micrograph of an LFT fracture surface, post impact, showing the fiber shearout and pullout along the highly oriented fracture plane.

A BOI from a conical (or pointed) impactor in comparison to an identical mass flat impactor, resulted in 26% lesser energy absorption to cause full penetration. Damage spread was along preferential fiber orientations in both cases, however the damage from the conical tip impactor caused radial cracking from the point of impact, while for the flat end the fracture paths were random.

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